

"A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON PRICE SPREADS AND MARKETING EFFICIENCY OF BANANA"

Bhosale, K. S., Jambhale, A. A., Rede, B. H., Deokate, P. S., Shitole, P. A., Balpuri, P. S., Lawate, S. M

Dr. Sharadchandra Pawar College of Agriculture,

Baramati, Maharashtra, India 413105

MS Received: 10.09.2024; MS Revised: 16.09.2024; MS Accepted: 17.09.2024

MS 3279

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURE,)

Abstract:

Banana is the most widely traded and popular fruit in the world, coming in second only to citrus. Banana fruits and leaves are in constant demand in the market. Banana production generates labour and profit for farmers. Purpose of the present study was to estimate price spread and marketing efficiency of banana. This study was conducted in the Pune district of Maharashtra, specifically targeting two tahsils: Baramati and Indapur, selected purposively on the basis of maximum area under banana cultivation. Three villages from each tahsil were randomly selected, resulting in a total of six villages. From these villages, 90 banana farmers were chosen. The primary data gathered for the agricultural year 2023-24. Three marketing channels were identified for banana, with Channel III comprising Producer - Wholesaler- Retailer- Consumer, being the most favored by farmers. The average price spread per quintal of banana was ₹ 66.84 for Channel I, ₹ 2,204.50 for Channel II and ₹ 2,436.50 for Channel III. Also, marketing efficiency was maximum for Channel-I (12.41), followed by Channel - II (1.47) and Channel - III (1.51).

Key Words: Banana, Marketing cost, Marketing channels, Price spread, Market efficiency.

Introduction:

Banana (*Musa paradisiaca* L.) is a member of the Musaceae family. The origin of banana is South East Asia. The banana was classified as a fruit crop or cash crop in modern agricultural classifications along with rice, oil palm, sugarcane, pineapple, and mango. Banana is the most widely traded and popular fruit in the world, coming in second only to citrus. Banana fruits and leaves are in constant demand in the market. Banana production generates labour and profit for farmers. Banana, a highly perishable fruit, is being marketed in a short period of time. As a result, using a systematic set of banana methods will significantly increase productivity.

The worldwide production of banana was 124 million tons in 2023. (Anonymous, 2023). Area, production and productivity of banana in India is 995.19 thousand ha, 37474.18 thousand MT and 37.66 MT/ha, respectively. Similarly, In Maharashtra, Area, Production and productivity of banana are 111 thousand ha, 6525.87 thousand MT and 58.79 MT/ha, respectively. (Anonymous, 2023-24). Districts in Maharashtra included Nanded, Jalgaon, Solapur, Nandurbar, and Pune having maximum production.

Materials and Methods:

The sample for the study necessary involved the selection of area i.e. district, tehsils, villages and cultivators as well as markets. Initially Pune district was purposively selected for the present study. The district is divided into 14 tehsils and out of them Indapur and Baramati tehsils have a large proportion of areas under banana cultivation. so, at the second stage two tehsils i.e. Baramati and Indapur were selected. Three villages from each tahsil were purposively selected, resulting in a total of six villages. A sample of 15 banana growers were randomly selected from each village. Thus, the total 90 banana growers were selected for the present study.

Tools of Analysis:

Total Marketing Cost: For calculating total marketing cost, this formula was used.

$$C = Cr + Cm1 + Cm2 + \dots + Cm_n$$

Where,

C = Total marketing cost

Cr = Cost paid by the producer from the time the produce leaves the farm till he sells it.

Cm = Cost incurred by its middleman in the process of buying and selling the product.

Marketing Margin: The intermediary's margin is the difference between the total market payments he makes during his transaction. For obtaining marketing margin following formula was used.

$$MT = \sum (Si - Pi) / Qi$$

Where,

MT = Total Marketing Value

Si = Sell value of a product paid by ith firmPi = Purchase value of product paid by ith firmQi = Quantity of product handled by ith firm

Price Spread: Price spread means difference between consumer's price and price received by the farmer. In this study, price spread covered the overall cost of marketing as well as the profit or loss made by intermediaries in the process of moving produce from the farm to the customer.

$$Ps = Cp - Pf$$

Where,

Cp = Consumer's Price

Pf = Price received by the farmer

Marketing Efficiency (ME): The marketing efficiency was calculated by using the modified method suggested by Achary and Agarwal (2001).

$$MME = RP / (MC + MM)$$

Where,

MME = Modified measure of marketing efficiency

RP = Price paid by consumer or retailers sell price

MC = Total marketing cost MM = Net marketing margin

Result and Discussion:

The following were significant marketing channels in the banana marketing observed during the study:

I. Producer – Consumer

II. Producer- Pre harvest contractor - Wholesaler- Retailer- Consumer.

III. Producer - Wholesaler- Retailer- Consumer.

Cost of marketing Banana

Marketing involves several functions such as Loading-Unloading, packing, transporting, and handling of produce. The cost of conducting these activities is essential in banana marketing because it affects consumer prices as well as producer profits.

Table 1. shows the costs incurred by banana producers for operations such as Loading-unloading, packing, transportation and commissions.

Table 1. Channel wise per quintal marketing cost incurred by banana farmers

(Rs./ q)			
Sr.No.	Particulars	Channel II	Channel III
A	Marketing cost incurred by farmer	-	-
B	Marketing cost incurred by village trader		
1.	Commission	37.5	-
2.	Transportation	63.5	-

3.	Loading and Unloading	34	-
4.	Weighing	17.5	-
5.	Other	445	-
	Sub total	597.5	-
C	Marketing cost incurred by wholesaler		
1.	Transportation	25	42.5
2.	Loading and Unloading	57.5	175
3.	Storage	42.5	160
4.	Packaging cost	290	22.5
5.	market fees	20	20
6.	Losses	30	287.5
7.	Commission	275	275
8.	Other	15	570
	sub total	755	1552.5
D	Marketing cost incurred by retailer		
1.	Transportation	47.5	39
2.	Loading and unloading	35	25
3.	market fees	20	20
4.	Losses	30	287.5
5.	Other	27	17.5
6.	Commission	190	110
	Sub total	349.5	499
	Total	1702	2051.5

The table shows that Channel-II and Channel-III spent Rs.1702 and Rs. 2051.5 per quintal to Banana marketing, respectively. Out of these in Channel-II, Marketing cost accumulated by Pre harvest contractor, Wholesaler and Retailer were Rs.597.5, Rs.755 and Rs. 349.5, respectively.

In Channel-III, Marketing cost incurred by Wholesaler and Retailer were Rs.1552.5 and Rs.499, respectively. In Channel II, the produce was sold at the farm gate before harvest. Farmers did not face any Marketing cost for marketing their produce.

Price spread in different marketing channels of banana

The price spread is the difference between how much the consumer pays and what the producer receives. This includes the margins of the various channels and marketing expenditures. The margins and costs

Table 4.15. Price spread in different channels of Banana

of agency in various channels were calculated, and specifics are shown in Table 2.

The table shows that the producer received a net price of Rs.762.84 in channel-I, Rs. 1025.23 in channel-II and Rs.1230.47 in channel-III. The price spread was lowest in channel-I (Producer- Consumer), due to low marketing expenditures and market margins between producer and consumer. The largest price spread in channel-III was Rs. 2436.50. This was according to the increased number of market places involved. The estimated producers' share of the consumer rupee in Channels I, II and III was 91.94, 31.74 and 33.56 percent, respectively. The preceding discussion suggests that Channel-I was more profitable than Channel-II and Channel-III. Additionally, the Banana farmers have earned Maximum share of consumer prices.

Sr. No.	Particulars	(Rs./q)		
		Channel I	Channel II	Channel III
1	Gross price received by the farmer	829.68 (100)	1025.23 (31.74)	1230.47 (33.56)
	i) Marketing cost	66.84 (8.06)	-	-
	ii) Net price realized	762.84 (91.94)	1025.23 (31.74)	1230.47 (33.56)
2	Village Trader			
	i) Price paid	-	1025.23 (31.74)	-
	ii) Marketing cost	-	597.5 (18.5)	-
	iii) Marketing margin	-	37.5 (1.16)	-
	iv) price received	-	1660.23 (51.4)	-
3	Wholesaler			

	i) Price paid	-	1660.23 (51.4)	1230.47 (33.56)
	ii) Marketing cost	-	755 (23.38)	1552.5 (42.33)
	iii) Marketing margin	-	275 (8.51)	275 (7.50)
	iv) Price Received	-	2690.23 (83.3)	3057.97 (83.39)
	Retailer			
	i) Price paid	-	2690.23 (83.3)	3057.97 (83.39)
	ii) Marketing cost	-	349.5 (10.82)	499 (13.61)
	iii) Marketing margin	-	190 (5.88)	110 (3.00)
	iv) Price Received	-	3229.73 (100)	3666.97 (100)
5	Consumer Price Paid	829.68 (100)	3229.23 (100)	3666.97 (100.00)
	Price Spread	66.84	2204.50	2436.50

(Figures in the parentheses is the percentages to the price paid by consumer)

Channel wise marketing efficiency of Banana

Marketing Efficiency was examined using a modified method proposed by Acharya and Aggarwal (1999). According to Table 3, the Marketing Efficiency was maximum for Channel-I (12.41), followed by Channel - II (1.47) and Channel - III (1.51).

The findings coincided with Vignesh *et al.*, (2022), Rede *et al.* (2021). Thus, the hypothesis stated that market costs have a large impact on the market efficiency of banana is proven.

Conclusion:

The average per qtl. Marketing cost at channel I, channel II and channel III were ₹ 66.84, ₹1,702, and ₹2,051.5, respectively. The key marketing costs were transportation, grading, packaging, and so on.

The price spreads in channels I, II and III were ₹ 66.84, ₹ 2,204.50 and ₹ 2,436.50, respectively. The maximum marketing efficiency was 12.41 in Channel I. The higher the number of market intermediaries, the lower the marketing efficiency.

References:

1. **Anonymous, 2023-** 20224, indiastat.
2. Anonymous, 2023, FAOSTAT.
3. **Krishna, M. R., Kumar, K. N. and Bhavani Devi, I. 2017.** A Micro Economic analysis of production of banana in Kurnool district of Andhra Pradesh, India, International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences, **6**(7): 1152-1159.
4. **Kumar, S. and Tegar, A. 2021.** An economic analysis of production and marketing of banana in Bilaspur district of Chhattisgarh state, The Pharma Innovation Journal, **10** (10): 466-468.
5. **Kumari, P., Kumar, S. and Ratnam, S. 2018.** Price spread and marketing of banana in vaishali district (Bihar), International Journal of Chemical Studies, **6**(3): 1966- 1969.

6. **Nayak, A. N., Singhand, N. and Kumar, D. 2018.** An economic analysis of marketing of banana (*Musa paradisiaca* L.) in Durg district of Chhattisgarh, International Research Journal of Agricultural Economics and Statistics, **9**(1): 1- 8.
7. **Patel, A., Jain, B. C., Sharma, S. and Sai, Y. K. 2018.** Production and marketing of banana in Bemetara district of Chhattisgarh: An economic analysis, Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry, **7**(2): 2021-2023
8. **Patowary, M., Kumar, S. and Singh, V. 2022.** A Study on Marketing aspects of Banana in Goalpara District of Assam, Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Science, **15**(5): 01-08.
9. **Permadi, R., Bachri, A. A., Fauzi, M. and Hamdani. 2022.** Investigation of saba banana marketing efficiency: structure, conduct and performance approach, International Journal of Biosciences, **20**(4): 106-120.
10. **Rajendran, T., Pradeepkumar, S. T. and Suruthi, M. 2018.** Price spread, marketing channel of banana in Southern Tamilnadu. International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (IJTSRD), **1**(2): 123-128.
11. **Raman, M. S. and Umanath, M. 2016.** Production and marketing of banana in Tiruchirapalli district of Tamil Nadu: An economic analysis, International Research Journal of Agricultural Economics and Statistics, **7**(1): 67-75.
12. **Rede, B. H., Ratnaparkhe, A. N., Yadav, J. P. and Shinde, H. R. 2021.** Economic analysis of marketing of banana in Solapur district of Maharashtra, The Pharma Innovation Journal, **10**(12): 149-153.
13. **Vignesh, M., Selvakumar, R. and Azhagesan, R. 2022.** An economic analysis of trend, cost and returns of banana in kanniyakumari district of tamilnadu, Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR), **9**(9): 223 - 229.